

Ultrasonic velocity studies on $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ nanoferrofluid prepared by co-precipitation method

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Abstract

Nanoferrofluids of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ were prepared by chemical co-precipitation method by varying the value of x (0.1, 0.3, and 0.5M). The structural characterization done by X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirms the formation of spinel ferrite structure. The crystallite size of the samples calculated using Scherrer formula from the full width half maximum of (3 1 1) plane are in the range of 33 – 42 nm. The crystallite size of the sample increases with increase in nickel content. The surface morphological investigation was done by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique. The ultrasonic velocity of nickel doped Cobalt nanoferrofluids was measured by varying the temperature in the range of 30-70 °C. The ultrasonic velocities of magnetic nanoferrofluids decrease with increase in nickel concentration. The higher value of velocity of nanoferrofluid than that of the carrier liquid in the absence of magnetic field shows the influence of dispersed particles on the velocity of ultrasonic propagation.

Keywords: Nanoferrofluids, Ultrasonic velocity, Crystallite Size, Co-precipitation method